

PREVALENCE OF DENTAL DISEASES IN ADOLESCENT GIRLS

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Relevance of the study.

Considerable work has been carried out in developing primary prevention of dental diseases, improving its clinical and dental effectiveness, and enhancing the dental care system. However, studies devoted to analyzing and interpreting the results of dental health status among adolescent girls remain incomplete. There is still a need to reduce the incidence of these diseases, develop effective primary prevention methods, and improve the quality of life of adolescent girls. Therefore, continuing research in this area and implementing optimal preventive programs into practice remain pressing issues.

Aim of the study.

To improve the study of the prevalence of dental diseases in adolescent girls.

Object of the study.

Adolescent girls diagnosed with dental diseases were selected.

Results and analysis.

The study of dental health and assessment of dental status in adolescent girls began with collecting patients' life history (anamnesis), which is the first stage of examination. In addition to identifying complaints indicating disease symptoms, surveys made it possible to clarify clinical manifestations.

It was found that all examined patients reported tooth pain at the initial onset of the disease. Objective examination results were analyzed based on pathological changes in the hard tissues of teeth and the oral mucosa. During clinical and functional examination, attention was also paid to exacerbation periods of dental diseases.

Dental examinations of adolescent girls were conducted according to generally accepted schemes. All data were recorded in patients' medical histories. Examination began with an external facial assessment. Particular attention was given to facial asymmetry, general appearance, presence of lesions or swelling on the red border of the lips, as well as the condition and color of skin, nails, mucous membranes, and presence of edema or spots.

In examined patients, swelling and infiltration of facial soft tissues were objectively detected. When masticatory muscles were involved in inflammatory processes, inflammatory contracture of the lower jaw was observed. Among complications of dental diseases in adolescent girls, thickening of the alveolar process of the jaw and

purulent discharge from under the gums were noted. Swelling of the gingiva and transitional folds in the affected tooth area was also observed.

Table 1. Distribution of prevalence rates of dental diseases among adolescent girls by regions

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Distribution of prevalence rates of dental diseases among adolescent girls by regions

Diagnosis	Bogot district (n=986)	Yangibazar district (n=933)	Urgench city (n=855)
Moderate caries	17,85±1,22	18,01±1,26	10,18±1,07*
Deep caries	17,04±1,20	16,93±1,23	14,62±1,21
Acute focal pulpitis	16,23±1,17	15,65±0,51	14,15±1,19
Chronic periodontitis	14,81±1,13	16,93±1,23	16,14±1,26
Gingivitis	11,76±1,03	10,18±0,99	6,78±0,86*
Periodontosis	10,95±0,99	10,06±0,98	4,91±0,74*
Wedge-shaped defect	6,29±0,77	4,93±0,71	6,67±0,85
Periodontitis	5,58±0,73	5,79±0,76	2,46±0,53*
Dental calculus	8,92±0,91	10,29±0,99	7,72±0,91
Chronic fibrous pulpitis	0,30±0,17	0,11±0,10	0/0
Chronic hypertrophic pulpitis	0,20±0,14	0/0	0/0

Painful palpation along the transitional fold was recorded based on patient complaints in medical records. During examination, general clinical indicators (blood pressure, pulse rate, respiratory rate) and additional tests (complete blood count, urinalysis, blood glucose level, coagulogram, aminotransferases, creatinine, urea, bilirubin levels, radiological diagnostics, ECG) were used.

Examination of the tongue included assessment of papillae condition and presence of coating. Examination of the oral vestibule and cheeks focused on moisture and color of the mucosa, as well as presence of tooth imprints.

General clinical methods, including visual and instrumental assessment of periodontal soft tissues, were applied. Clinical-functional tests were used to determine gingival condition. Inflammatory reactions were identified using the papillary-marginal index and the Green-Vermillion oral hygiene index.

Diagnosis was established based on anamnesis, complaints, clinical signs, and additional examination methods. Since visual assessment does not always accurately reflect the condition of gingival mucosa, simple and extended gingivostomy (in 61% of cases) was performed. This method was used when boundaries of inflammation were unclear and when it was difficult to assess the extent of epithelial damage and spread of inflammation to gingival papillae, marginal and alveolar gingiva.

Three degrees of hyperemia were observed:
1 – mild;
2 – moderate;
3 – severe;
as well as two staining degrees (1 and 2).

Conclusion.

The oral cavity was examined using a set of dental instruments under natural and artificial lighting. During examination, the depth of the oral cavity, level of oral hygiene, and condition of mucosa and periodontium were assessed. Special attention was paid to mucosal color, presence of edema, pain on palpation of gingival margin, bleeding during brushing or consumption of solid food, and presence of halitosis. All pathological changes detected in the oral cavity were recorded in outpatient records, including during initial examination, treatment, and follow-up periods. Changes in each tooth, periodontal tissue, and lesion area were systematically documented.

References:

1. Курязов А.К. Распространенность и интенсивность кариеса зубов среди беременных, проживающих в различных экологических условиях Узбекистана // Проблемы биологии и медицины. - Самарканд, 2010. - №3. – С.99-102 (14.00.00; №19).
2. Курязов А.К., Суванов К.Ж., Рузметов У.А. Особенности профилактики стоматологических заболеваний у беременных в условиях экологического неблагополучия. // Проблемы биологии и медицины. - Самарканд, 2010.- №3. - С.42-45 (14.00.00; №19).
3. Курязов А.К., Суванов К.Ж., Нуралиев Н.А. Сравнительное изучение факторов местного иммунитета ротовой полости у беременных женщин. // Журнал теоретической и клинической медицины. – Ташкент.- 2010. - № 5.- С. 86-89 (14.00.00 ; №3).
4. Курязов А.К., Суванов К.Ж. Распространенность болезней пародонта и слизистой оболочки полости рта среди беременных, проживающих в различных экологических условиях // Бюллетень ассоциации врачей Узбекистана. – Ташкент, 2011. - №1. – С. 78-82 (14.00.00; №17).

5. Kuryazov A.K., Nuraliyev N.A. Condition of non-specific protection factors of oral cavity among pregnant women // European journal of natural history. - 2012. - N 8. - P. 4-5 (Scopus).
6. Suvonov K.J., Adilov U.X., Kuryazov.A.K. Prevalence and risk factors of dental diseases in pregnant women living in different regions of Uzbekistan // European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. - 2020. - Vol. 07, Issue S-02, P.- 2864-2870 (Scopus).